

POLITICAL SCIENCES

POLITICAL MECHANISMS OF DEMOCRACY: ESTABLISHMENT OF POLITICAL INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The article explores the formation of political mechanisms of democracy and the establishment of political institutions. The importance of the establishment of political institutions to ensure the sustainability of democratic governance, to enhance the effectiveness of governance, and to ensure the legal relationship between the state and society is emphasized. By analyzing various political institutions, the role and importance of their democratic governance are clarified. The raised issues are based on systematic and comparative analysis and come to a specific conclusion.

Keywords: democracy, political mechanism, political institutions, elections, parliamentarism, pluralism, referendum.

Introduction

Democracy reflects political and social institutions. It is through these political and social institutions that the political mechanisms of democracy are formed and operate. These institutions include the following: election and referendum institutions, representative and direct (direct) democracy institutions, parliament, executive and judicial authorities, legal institutions, political parties and other socio-political organizations, mass media, local self-government bodies and others.

When examining the structure of the political mechanism of democracy, it is possible to compare it according to the basic principles of democracy, government institutions, their legitimacy, the concrete realization of human rights and freedoms, as well as the level of political decision-making and political participation in this important process.

The article analyzes the importance of the role of establishing political institutions in the formation of the political mechanism of democracy. It is explained that this is very important for the realization of a democratic society. Because it is possible only in this case to have the influence mechanism of the institutions, efficient and effective working opportunities.

1. Conceptual approach to institutionalism

The society's transition to democracy is strengthened by the institutionalization of the political mechanisms of the new state power. M. Oriu, trying to explain the necessity of the relationship between the state and other social institutions, notes that "the state should be considered as an institution of institutions" [1].

Institutionalization refers to:

- establishment of institutions of parliamentarism or presidential democracy;
- prepare the legal bases that clearly define the powers of the division of power;
- to create appropriate structures of all three branches of government at different levels, etc.

The institutionalization of the new power system is strengthened by the Constitution, which ensures its

legitimacy. The institutional and constitutional establishment of the democratic regime is inseparable from the reform of the state apparatus. Because the ruling elite is changing here. This process has its own rules and contradictions. Legitimacy - implies the support and justification of the use of power and the implementation of a certain form of management either by the state as a whole or by its individual structures and institutions [2, p. 100-135].

The transition to democracy requires the formation of appropriate institutions of the civil society, the participation of citizens of different strata of the population in political processes, the creation of socio-political organizations and various associations that can realize their interests and achieve the realization of the political course of the government. Freedom flourishes when a society manages to create institutions that ensure its stability and long-term existence. According to Ralph Darendorf, "facilities, for example, are the framework we choose for our economic prosperity. Institutions provide us with the guarantee of our rights and therefore social justice"[3].

In the process of strengthening the civil society, as its diversity increases, the country adapts to the new regime. The loyalty of the former elite - the majority of various layers of the bureaucracy, military circles, political opposition - to the new regime is obtained. On the basis of new circles, new ideology, political and social forces are being strengthened. With the development of civil society, conditions are created for the comparison of ideas, views, and positions. Only in this way, it is possible to achieve a truly democratic strengthening of society and its development within the framework of new common basic values, not by forcing the views of the minority to be accepted by the majority. Of course, if the new regime prepares and implements a political course that meets the interests of the majority, not only political rights and freedoms, and if it achieves a noticeable improvement of the entire complex of living conditions, then it gets the support of that majority. The constant attainment of such support is the

basis of a democratic structure. At the same time, the protection of the government by the people does not exclude the right to express dissatisfaction with individual views and actions, and the possibility of constructive opposition.

A true democracy is a system of socio-political relations in which the government is elected by the people, and if necessary, removed from power by the will of the people and without the use of force. According to the representatives of the concept of democracy based on competition, the ideal of democracy is the celebration of the principle of balance of the free will of citizens and individuals. These or other theories, which accept democracy formally as the rule of the people elected by the people and for the people, make interrelated propositions without which democracy in any sense is impossible. In other words, democracy is a field of collective decisions. Democracy represents an ideal system in which decisions concerning society or any social group are made by all members. At the same time, those members have the right to participate equally in making these or other decisions [4, p.127]. It can be concluded from this that democracy requires public control over collective decisions and realization of the principle of equality of rights in the implementation of this control. Based on these principles, the political mechanisms of citizens' participation in the democratic management system are formed.

In itself, the recognition of general principles as elements of democracy does not mean that they have been fully realized in political reality. Only agreement between democratic views and actions creates real democracy.

2. The institution of parliamentarism

The formation of the institution of parliamentarism as one of the main political mechanisms of democracy is of particular importance. Political democracy is reflected in the institution of parliamentarism. Parliamentarianism is an integral part of a democratic regime, but parliamentarianism is not the only system of governance. In addition to parliamentarism, Western countries have presidential democracy (typical American model) and a collegial system like Switzerland.

Parliamentarianism is a complex institution of state building and administration and is based on representative democracy. The concept of "parliamentarism" reflects the system of legal, political and moral norms, traditions, "rules of the game" at various levels developed in the process of historical-political experience and realized in state administration. The main principles of democracy - people's sovereignty, majority rule, representation, pluralism form the basis of parliamentarism.

Parliament is elected by the people and governs on behalf of the people. In turn, the people exercise control over their representatives through elections as sovereigns. The powers of the elected deputies are determined and limited by the Constitution, which reflects the national consensus.

The Parliament reflects the majority of all socially important strata of the population; in addition, the decision-making mechanism is adopted by the "majority" principle (while respecting the opinion of the minority);

opposition is a necessary institution of parliamentarism.

The functioning of parliamentarism is the real implementation of the principle of pluralism in political practice. The election of parliamentarians on the party list, the activity of party factions, including the opposition factions, are concrete forms of meeting the program visions and concepts, political views of various political groups, expressing the spectrum of interests and ideas of voters.

The power function of the parliament is a derivative of the people's sovereignty and has a constitutional guarantee. Its most important activity is legislative activity. The composition of the power function also includes political control and bringing to responsibility the administrative subjects who violate the constitutional principles and norms.

Parliament is the most important institution for legitimizing state power, as it represents the majority of society and implements its will. Political legitimacy is realized by making political decisions that are in the interest of the society. Decisions made by representatives of the people are necessary for all state and public institutions, and the law is fundamental for those who govern and those who are governed.

Parliamentary democracy also institutionalizes social conflicts. Those elected by the people discuss and resolve the conflicts that have arisen in the society based on the generally accepted norms and "rules of the game" in an apparently legitimate manner.

The real power role of the parliament, the actual influence of the institution of parliamentarism on the political life of the democratic regimes as a whole depends on the order of the constitutional division of power in each country. The principle of separation of powers is the basis of parliamentarism. Otherwise, if you do not limit the powers of the parliament, it can become a destructive force, because making a decision based on the opinion of the majority does not guarantee the constructiveness and democracy of the decision [5].

Parliament, as a political institution, reveals the necessity of competition of its political forces. The competition, the competition within the framework of generally accepted "rules of the game", serves as a method of stimulating the political activity of political forces and selecting decision options. Parliamentary competition is the best way to reveal political leaders and educate them. In democratic countries, opposition is viewed as a normal and natural state of democracy.

Ensuring the rule of law is unequivocally the most important principle for the normal operation of the above-mentioned institutions. The powers of those in power are determined only by laws. The law prevents the government from having unlimited power over the governed (that is, it determines that they must do what the law requires, not how they want). On the other hand, the law facilitates the work of the administrators. Every citizen understands his responsibility before the laws and behaves accordingly. Everyone knows well that regardless of social status and position, punishment for breaking the law is absolute. Therefore, the behavior and activity of everyone in accordance with the requirements of the law allows for a better organization of

management. Every citizen believes and trusts in the supremacy of the laws developed in accordance with his interests, the policy of the government and considers it his duty to follow it. As a result, this forms a sense of mutual trust and confidence in nation-state relations.

3. People's sovereignty and electoral institution

The main essence of the principle of people's sovereignty, which is the main idea of people's power as a moral concept of democracy, is that the people are the source of the supreme political power in society. This principle is also reflected in the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

The principle of popular sovereignty refers to the following:

- constitutional power in the state belongs to the people; the people elect their representatives and may periodically change them; the people can directly participate in the development and adoption of laws through popular initiative and referendums; recognition of the government by the people is the basis of the legitimacy of the existing government.

The principle of people's power was directly related to the issue of democracy. Direct democracy is a form of organization and management of public life in which the people or their representatives directly participate in the implementation of the functions of state power. In the words of J. J. Russo, the unified will of the people completely coincides with the will of the state.

The principle of people's sovereignty is closely related to the principles of "majority" and "representation". The principle of "majority" is accepted by everyone, including liberals, conservatives, communists, and socialists. U. Rostow, one of the modern American sociologists, believes that democracy means statehood implemented on the basis of agreement between the governed and the governing majority [6, p. 324-335].

The principles and institutions of democracy are realized in various procedures (technologies of democracy) developed in political practice. These procedures are elections, voting, plebiscite, referendums, negotiations and compromises. In other words, the main factor in the formation of the political mechanism of democracy is the holding of free and democratic elections. The existence of a free and democratic electoral system and institution is the basis of the political mechanism of democracy. The completeness of democracy depends more on the technique of the electoral institution itself, the way in which the supreme legislative and executive authorities are elected, the rules for the election of authorities and administrative bodies below it, the extent to which the voters have the right to choose, the extent to which the right to vote is common to all, the voting is open or it depends on its secrecy, whether the elections are held periodically or not, and the degree of expression of citizens' free will.

It should also be emphasized that elections, which are an important principle for democracy, are also the biggest weapon in the hands of the people, through which they directly ensure their participation in the formation of power. Elections also determine the government's responsibility to the people and make it more attentive to its activities. The government is guided by

the interests of the people in its activities and decision-making (the highest goal of every state is to ensure human and civil rights and freedoms and a decent standard of living). He understands his responsibility before the people and does not forget that he has to report to it. Because the people always have the chance to use their sovereign rights [7].

Political representation has two main implications. First, a parliamentary representative acts as an agent of his constituents "accepted by them", "speaking on their behalf" and "defending their rights". In some cases, he acts on behalf of all voters.

The second concept of political representation is microcosmic and refers not to individual representatives of a representative body, but to the body itself as a whole. The legislature is considered representative to the extent that it reflects the character of the electorate as a whole in terms of some important aspects: social composition, territorial distribution, and the protection of individual parties.

The first aspect of political representation embodies the two basic principles of democracy mentioned above. According to the principle of the sovereignty of the people, all political power originates from the people, and the parliament and the government are controlled by them, this principle is reflected in the fact that the member of the representative body is in itself a kind of agent of the electorate. He is represented by the electorate, he acts in the interests of the electorate, he reports to it and can be replaced by it. The second aspect of the activity of members of representative bodies reflects the principle of political equality: all voters are equal, regardless of where they live and which party they vote for [8, p.51-53].

The principle of representation realized through the electoral system has the essence of democracy when it accepts the equality of citizens' participation in the political process. Democracy is a system that ensures the participation of all citizens in making political decisions. Its content is a set of rights that give everyone the opportunity to be elected to the power and management structure, to control the activities of ruling circles together with others, and if necessary, to change them by voting. Of course, this equality is formal, because it does not guarantee everyone to be a real participant. Political equality becomes real when it is sufficiently based on the social base of all sections of the population.

A. Tocqueville first discussed the problems of the dichotomy of the concepts of freedom and equality in his work "Democracy in America" [9]. The American political scientist and sociologist R. Dahl, as a result of many years, gave an analysis of the ideal of political democracy and the practice of realizing the principles of democratic governance in a concrete society in his works entitled "Introduction to Economic Democracy", "Introduction to Democracy", "Polyarchy", "Democracy and its Criticism" comprehensively criticized the concepts of equality. Expressing his opinion on A. Tocqueville's attitude to the concepts of freedom and equality, R. Dahl writes: "... A well-organized society ultimately requires three things: political equality, political freedom and economic freedom; Conditions in

the United States gave Americans the opportunity to advance in the direction of these three goals" [10, p. 13].

However, time has not yet eliminated the conflict between political equality and freedom, regardless of the individual's economic and social independence. If we look at the process in a broad framework, we can see that R. Dahl himself is worried about the possibility of such a conflict intensifying in the United States. If in the political sphere, despite all the contradictions, the basic political rights are expanding and strengthening, then in the economic sphere, the sphere of influence of democratic principles narrows to the extent of the creation and expansion of large economic structures. In addition, the unrestricted nature of free enterprise creates economic inequality, which in turn threatens political democracy.

Touching on the principles of equality and freedom in the book "Lessons of Democracy", Roland Watson shows that "there can be no question of freedom without equality. Although equality seems to be superior to freedom here, only the latter remains the goal [11, pp. 6-7].

In the formation of the political mechanism of democracy, the participation of all the people in solving the fateful issues of the society and the nation - the referendum - is of great importance. The referendum considers the most important issues important to the society to be resolved through a national vote, the obtained result has the highest legal status and is mandatory for the implementation of all state bodies. Referendum is used as a legislative mechanism in most democratic countries of the world. As a whole, it functions as a legislative mechanism, especially at the local level, despite its subordination to the legislative activity of the parliament.

There are differences in the right to initiate a referendum in different countries. In some countries (Great Britain, Sweden, Norway, etc.), the initiator of the referendum is only the parliament and the government, in others (for example, France) the president is the initiator of the referendum, and in others (Switzerland, Austria, Italy) it is the people directly [12, p.267].

For the formation of the political mechanism of democracy, the establishment of the legal state and the civil society, their interaction is the main factor. The creation and strengthening of civil society, the strengthening of the democratization process, the establishment of a legal state is not just a slogan or an intention, but the main condition for the comprehensive development of the state [13, p. 147-148].

American political scientist Dankwart Rastow states that "Democracy is not a copy of the constitutional laws or parliamentary practice of some existing democracy, but the ability to honestly look at specific conflicts and invent or use effective mechanisms for their resolution." [14]

In order for political institutions to function effectively and efficiently in the process of democratization, V. Pantin notes that "it is important for political institutions to take into account the opinion and opinion of the

majority of the people, pay attention to legitimacy (legality), correctly assess problems and find a way out" [15]

The conclusion

The analysis of the effective formation of democratic regimes shows that democratic political institutions become effective only as a result of long-term development and the process of adaptation to the conditions and traditions of a certain society. Therefore, the high degree of democracy in Western countries should be discussed only in the 20th century. As a result, the current difficulties in the establishment of democratic political institutions in a number of countries are explained by the fact that democracy and its institutions can be effective only by gradually adapting to political realities, not by their compliance with national traditions and norms.

Also, in parallel with the positive influence of people's political consciousness and political culture on the establishment of democratic governance, their understanding of democratic principles and values creates conditions for more correct and flexible functioning of the governance structure.

The approval and development of new political institutions goes through three main stages. The first stage is the creation and formation of this institution, the second stage is its legalization, rooting in society and public consciousness, adaptation to customs and norms, and the third stage is the increase of its effectiveness. The second phase, as a rule, covers the longest period and may be accompanied by moves against authoritarianism, followed by new opportunities to build democratic institutions in a renewed form.

Institutionalization of political mechanisms allows the state to have a more stable and stable political system and a flexible management apparatus. At this time, rather than the role of individuals, the activity of state institutions as a functioning mechanism plays a key role. With this, the existence of these principles, which are important for a democratic society, provides comprehensive assistance in ensuring the sovereignty, military-political security, economic stability of the state, establishing an efficient model of mutual relations between the government-people, government-opposition in the country, and the normal development of the social-political process.

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